

WAYS TO ORGANIZE PROCUREMENT AND SUPPLY OF PRODUCTS IN THE ARMED FORCES SYSTEM BASED ON MARKET MECHANISMS

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Abstract: *Today, economic costs in the military sector are increasing worldwide. The demand for efficiency in the military economy, procurement and supply of products in the Armed Forces system is increasing. Issues of formation of product purchase and supply based on market mechanisms are discussed in this article.*

Key words: *purchase, conclusion of contracts, placing orders, purchase and supply of products, efficiency of department activity, purchase service, purchase service system, stages of purchase implementation, purchase application, purchase order, method of selecting product suppliers, system of working with product suppliers.*

INTRODUCTION

The military potential and military power of the state are directly determined by indicators of economic potential. The tasks and needs of the Armed Forces stimulate the production of not only weapons and military equipment, but also a wide range of consumer and industrial-technical products, as well as the development of various works and services.

The power of the Armed Forces of any country increases based on the potential of the country's economy. National defense plays an important role in the forecast of the country's economic security and macroeconomic budget indicators. National defense works in cooperation with relevant sectors of the economy, including fuel and lubricants, weapons and equipment, capital construction, clothing production, food industry.

It is important to use market mechanisms to strengthen the procurement and supply of products necessary for the Armed Forces. This article focuses on issues related to the purchase of products.

THE MAIN PART

The purchase and supply of products in the Armed Forces system is carried out as part of public procurement based on market mechanisms. One department and one employee of this department can deal with the procurement service in the free network and industry enterprises of the economy. In this case, purchasing functions are not divided into separate groups. In large enterprises, purchasing services are divided into separate groups, and it has a complex structure. Such a structured procurement service is presented in Figure 1.

In large enterprises, several dozen specialists deal with the purchase of raw materials and material resources. Employees of the purchasing department find suppliers of products, analyze their possibilities, agree and determine the prices, agree

on the duration and other conditions of the contract. Such activity can be specialized according to the types and types of purchased goods. Specialization is divided into groups according to the types of raw materials and material resources. In the structure of the procurement manager, agencies for procurement of raw materials, procurement of fuels and lubricants, procurement of equipment, and other procurements can be established.

Expedition Manager. This group monitors and examines how suppliers are meeting their obligations regarding product delivery and quality. If there is a problem, they will help to solve it.

The data processing or administrative group prepares and formalizes all the documents necessary for the operation of the purchasing department and is engaged in the preparation of periodic information for the head of the enterprise and the purchasing department. Employees of this department use electronic methods of information exchange, relying on a computer-generated database.

The procurement analytics team is tasked with creating custom data analysis projects in order to make better purchasing decisions.

The purchase is carried out in the following stages:

1. The composition and amount of purchased material resources is determined;
2. Sources of supply are determined;
3. Terms of the contract are agreed and a contract is concluded;
4. Purchase orders are formed;
5. The fulfillment of orders is monitored;
6. Material resources are checked and accepted in terms of quantity and quality;

7. Payment for material resources is made.

In the Armed Forces system, the purchase of important products such as fuel and lubricants, cargo and special vehicles and equipment, food products, clothing production, and radio communication equipment is carried out on the basis of the structure presented in Figure 1. These products are made based on military potential.

Procurement of products in the Armed Forces system includes stages consisting of certain sequences (Fig.2)

Figure 2. Stages of procurement of products in the Armed Forces system.

Procurement of products in the Armed Forces system is of particular importance, and it begins with the study of the existing demand and need. Specialists engaged in this type of activity study the individual needs of each unit and structure of the Armed Forces system. Determines what, how much and when is needed.

Summary

When organizing the purchase and supply of products in the Armed Forces system on the basis of market mechanisms, it is appropriate to pay attention to the following:

Finding external and internal sources of purchase, all information about purchased products, article, product group and other indicators should be on a standard basis.

When choosing supply sources, product suppliers who have the ability to deliver timely and quality resources, evaluate their supply potential, conclude contracts and agreements, and take them into account.

When evaluating potential suppliers, the following general indicators should be used: technical or engineering capabilities, production or distribution capabilities, financial potential and management ability. In some cases, a small amount of inspection can also be done by placing test orders.

It is advisable to form a portfolio of quarterly, annual, 5-year orders for certain times.

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